

Glimpses on Lab-Grown Meat

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Demand for meat is increasing and the supply of animals like cows, pigs, chickens used for meat, diminishing due to issues of commercial production of them. Commercial livestock production is becoming unviable on a global scale in terms of animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and human health. Options for artificial meat are being explored using techniques like stem cells, satellite cells or myoblasts, Embryonic Stem Cells, Induced pluripotent stem cells, Totipotent stem cells, pluripotent stem cells, etc. In this method, animal tissue is grown in a controlled environment using cell culture technology. There are attempts made to develop different types of media and techniques like the Self-organizing techniques and Scaffold-based techniques to grow the cell further. Cultured meat is also called 'clean meat', 'in-vitro meat', 'artificial meat', or even 'alt-meat'. The concept is in the infant stage of commercialization hence along with the technical aspect there is a lot of work is being done in the environmental, commercial, social, economic, and ethical aspects of the concept. The real benefits and cost as compared to current methods of meat production are still to be explored.

Keywords: Lab-Grown Meat, animal farming.

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Introduction

Demand for meat is increasing and the supply of animals like cows, pigs, chickens used for meat, diminishing due to issues of commercial production of them. Commercial livestock production is becoming unviable on a global scale in terms of animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and human health. Options for artificial meat are being explored using techniques like stem cells, satellite cells or myoblasts, Embryonic Stem Cells, Induced pluripotent stem cells, Totipotent stem cells, pluripotent stem cells, etc. In this method, animal tissue is grown in a controlled environment using cell culture technology. There are attempts made to develop different types of media and techniques like self-organizing techniques and Scaffold-based techniques to grow the cell further. Cultured meat is also called 'clean meat', 'in-vitro meat', 'artificial meat, or even 'alt-meat'. The concept is in the infant stage of commercialization hence along with the technical aspect there is a lot of work is being done in the environmental, commercial, social, economic, and ethical aspects of the concept. Thermal benefits and cost as compared to current methods of meat production are still to be explored.

Meat is a vital source of protein, iron, and many other nutritional requirements of the human diet for ages. Every year, more than 60 billion animals are reared in industrial conditions in order to produce meat. Animals grown in unnatural conditions like poultry farms, goat farms, cattle farms, etc. have resulted in numerous animal diseases like "Madcow", "Bird Flu", "Scombroid", which got transmitted to humans when such meat was consumed, forced to slaughter these animals and dispose of with care. Animal husbandry has another side effect that is choking the Earth by using about 70% of agricultural land for the fodder of these animals which has adverse effects on a natural resource such as the depletion of freshwater reservoirs, biodiversity loss, soil erosion, and destruction of habitats, etc. Livestock raising for meat, eggs, and milk generates around 15% of global greenhouse gas emissions, the second-highest source of emissions higher than all combined transport(1).

In 2016, it was seen that the US consumed about 97.1 Kg of meat per capita, per year, followed by Australia at 94.8 kg and then Argentina at 86.1 kg. The major exception to this pattern has been

India where the per capita meat consumption in 2013 was almost exactly the same as in 1961 at less than 4 kg per person. To solve the problems related to meat consumption on a global scale as well as meet the meat demand, cultured meat or lab-grown meat would play a vital role in the new era. The concept of cultured meat was popularized by Jason Matheny in early 2000. In 2013, Mark Post created the first lab-grown burger patty. Lab-grown meat production involves a multidisciplinary approach that includes biotechnology, tissue engineering, and molecular biology to create a new design to produce proteins and fats, and tissues. The startups developing lab-grown beef, pork, poultry, and seafood are MosaMeat, Memphis Meats, Super Meat, and FinlessFoods using modern techniques.

While research is ongoing, the attempt was made to produce the cultivated meat for space flights and the protein requirement of inhabitants of space stations. NASA cultured muscle tissue (obtained from common goldfish (*Carassius auratus*), ranging 3-10 cm in length, in Petri dishes (2). Muscle tissues cultured in crude cell extracts improved in cell mass. Such cells were later washed, dipped in olive oil and spices, coated with breadcrumbs, and fried and tasted with a taste panel that concluded that the product was palatable. One of the essential techniques of in-vitro meat production was to obtain and grow muscle tissues in an acceptable medium and to harvest them (2).

In vitro advanced meat engineering and tissue engineers have been involved in the selection process, putting adult cells on scaffolds, developing them in bioreactors, and using cultivated cells to produce muscle tissue(3). Certain programs aimed at using the proliferation of stem cells by putting them on top of each other and using inkjet techniques to spray cell materials on sheets or other structures (4) Researchers of the Cultured Beef Project remove muscle cells from the shoulder of a cow and feed the cells with a nutrient mixture in a petri dish. They grow into muscle tissue. It took three months to grow the beef using stem cells from a cow's shoulder. By tissue engineering technique it is possible to obtain tons of meat from a few starter cells. Mosa Meat, a Dutch company, launched its first hamburger in London in 2013. The burger included five ounces of grown meat (beef) patty, cooked and analyzed by

A panel of sensory experts in London, who found it tasted close to a regular burger. For this burger, the financial cost was over \$330,000. The event encouraged consumers, particularly those concerned with animal welfare, to support the commercial introduction of such meat products(5).

The company ' Super Meats ' has been working in Israel with the Hebrew University of Jerusalem for several years, and recent news reports suggest that three Israeli artificial meat companies – Super Meat, Future Meat Technology, and Meat the Future – will benefit from the \$300 million trade agreement signed between China and Israel (Roberts, 2017). Although this deal has been reported in the press, it is not yet publicly clear what this will mean for these firms, and none of them have yet announced publicly any demonstration products (6).

Global Scenario

Global meat production today stands at 263 million tonnes and is expected to nearly double again to 445 million tonnes by 2050 (1). India has also taken initiative in this sector. Institute of Chemical Technology (ICT), Mumbai, has joined hands with good Food Institute, a global non-profit organization engaged in and promoting the plant- and cell-based meat sector through research and commercialization, to establish a lab facility in Mumbai by 2020. Even FSSAI has also initiated very positive action for creating regulations for clean meat products but the big challenge is the product is not ready for any assessment but regulators have started discussions with all stakeholders and it is a very constructive and inspiring step (1).

Conclusion

It seems that by slowly replacing animal farming, large-scale agricultural meat production can significantly reduce animal suffering, the risk of human disease, and environmental problems. Government subsidies and an increased national budget for bio- and agro-technology research may be able to accelerate the production of cultivated products. Cultured meat would provide healthy, nutritious, and sustainable food for future generations with a rapidly growing global population. It would reduce food shortages, reduce food-borne diseases, reduce pollution, and increase the production of cultured meat. Cultured meat would minimize relying on natural resources and

Land resources, providing the opportunity to use that land for other recreational and beneficial purposes. Cultured meat technology is still in its experimental stage and has so far been limited to producing a small number of processed meat items in laboratory settings for demonstrative purposes. Recently the research is motivated on streamlining the production methods in order to reduce the cost, advancement of scalability, and minimize the requirement of animals as a source. Further research can be done on launching and marketing these products to build consumer`s trust, acceptance, and familiarity with the product.

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